

Methodological Compromise in the EVIDENCE trial: Why a Non-Significant Result Does Not Mean Equivalence

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The EVIDENCE trial¹ provides rare randomized data comparing flow diversion (FD) to coiling (\pm stent) for unruptured wide-necked intracranial aneurysms. However, its final non-significant main finding must be interpreted with caution due to critical methodological limitations regarding outcome definition, statistical power, and analytic transparency.

The original 2014 protocol (NCT01811134) specified 12-month complete angiographic occlusion with core-lab adjudication as the primary outcome; however, it used non-harmonized definitions (Raymond–Roy grade 1 for coiling and Kamran grade 4 for FD), precluding a single uniform definition across arms.² In May 2024, before unblinding, the steering committee prospectively amended the primary outcome to a hierarchical composite (“treatment failure”), which aggregated rare clinical events with retreatment and angiographic failure.¹ While intended to align with prior composites, this migrates the outcome away from the registered objective endpoint and complicates synthesis. Importantly, the paper reports the originally registered endpoint not as the primary result but as a secondary outcome: 82.9% complete occlusion with FD (34/41) versus 61.9% with coiling (26/42); RR 1.34 (95% CI, 1.02–1.76); $p=0.05$, a borderline signal limited by sample size (see Table).

In the original design, 130 patients were required to detect a 20% absolute difference in 12-month complete occlusion (FD 90% vs coiling 70%), based on early FD efficacy reports. Enrollment ended at 91 patients (≈ 87 analyzable). As the authors note, in 2024 the hypothesis was revised to a 25-point effect—expressed as failure reduction from 35% to 10%—to compensate for low accrual. The paper, however, cites no literature to anchor those rates. Moreover, if that 25-point revision is mapped back to the registered outcome (i.e., FD 90% vs coiling 65%), contemporary benchmarks for 12-month complete occlusion—FD ≈ 80 –85%³ and coiling ≈ 70 –75%⁴—support a more realistic margin of ≈ 10 –12 points, not 25. Taken together, the inflated assumed delta and the enrollment shortfall left the study underpowered for its superiority question; the wide 95% CI (0.35–1.83) on the primary outcome demonstrates the resulting imprecision.

Moreover, although EVIDENCE’s acronym commits to a medico-economic evaluation and the French government-funding supported cost-effectiveness², the incremental cost-effectiveness analysis was not reported in this article; posting the results module and protocol/statistical analysis plan to the registry would close the transparency gap.

Finally, two design features limit clinical inference: non-uniform mRS blinding and variably timed, incompletely observed “12-month” evaluations. Given minimal missingness in the composite outcome, an available-case intention-to-treat estimate with worst-case bounds suffices. However, for endpoints with greater missingness and timing dispersion (occlusion rate, mRS), the primary analysis should use multiple imputation with tipping-point sensitivity under missing-not-at-random assumptions, with available-case estimates as secondary.

EVIDENCE advances the field, but—read as designed and sized as executed—it yields signals, not verdicts. We commend the authors for publishing results they label non-significant; however, the absence of superiority for FD over coiling reflects statistical imprecision from under-enrollment and methodological changes, not equivalence. Definitive conclusions will require trials that retain objective, registered endpoints, plan realistic effect sizes accounting for attrition, and handle missing data with pre-specified, principled methods.

Table 1. Registered plan vs actual execution and statistical consequences

Item	Registered plan (protocol/registry)	Actual execution (publication)	Consequence
Primary outcome	Complete occlusion at 12 months (core-lab)	Composite “treatment failure”	Outcome migration; harder to compare with prior occlusion-focused evidence
Comparator	—	Coiling (\pm stent)	Clarify control strategy across analyses
Sample size & effect assumption	n=130 (~65/arm), assume $\Delta=20$ pp (FD 90% vs coiling 70%)	Hypothesis revised in 2024 (pre-unblinding) to $\Delta=25$ pp (FD 90% vs coiling 65%) to compensate for low enrollment	Design targeted a very large delta
Enrollment & analyzable	—	n=91 enrolled; 87 analyzable (~43/arm)	Marked shortfall vs plan
Detectability on registered outcome	—	—	Power ($\Delta=10$ pp): $\approx 18-21\%$ Power ($\Delta=12$ pp): $\approx 24-29\%$ MDE (80% power): $\approx 21-24$ pp [†]
Observed (angiographic, protocol-concordant)	—	FD 82.9% (34/41) vs coiling 61.9% (26/42); RR 1.34 (95% CI 1.02–1.76); p=0.05	Borderline signal; precision limited by n
Observed (composite primary)	—	RR 0.80 (95% CI 0.35–1.83); p=0.60	Wide CI \rightarrow imprecision, not equivalence
Outcome assessment (clinical)	—	mRS assessors not uniformly blinded	Risk of assessment bias for clinical endpoints
Timing & completeness of “12-month” assessments	—	Imaging ~ 13 mo (wide SD); mRS ~ 16 mo (very wide SD); incomplete observation	Increased variance; potential informative missingness

Power values use a two-proportion z-test (two-sided $\alpha=0.05$; 1:1 allocation; $n\approx 43$ per arm; no continuity correction). Estimates assume FD \approx control + Δ at ~ 12 months and are robust for control rates $\approx 65-75\%$. [†] MDE depends on control rate/endpoint: aneurysm occlusion ($p_0\approx 0.68-0.75$) $\approx 21-24$ pp; composite “treatment failure” ($p_0\approx 0.30-0.40$) $\approx 29-30$ pp (refined grid). Comparator = coiling with or without stent assistance. Abbreviations: FD, flow diversion; MDE, minimal detectable difference; n/N, number of participants (per group/total); pp, percentage points; RR, risk ratio.

References

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Disclaimer

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Competing Interests

H. Henkes is amongst several other devices the co-inventor of the Solitaire stent, the pRESET stent retriever, pCONUS bifurcation stent, p48/p64 flow diverter, pRELAX and pEGASUS stents, and was co-founder of phenox GmbH and femtos GmbH, which were medical device companies developing and/or selling products for the treatment of neurovascular disorders.

P. Albiña-Palmarola declares no conflicts of interest related to this work.